

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

OPPORTUNITIES TO IMPROVE ROAD, TRANSPORT AND PORT COOPERATION BETWEEN CHINA, MONGOLIA, AND RUSSIA

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Abstract

In this article we analyze the implementation of the Mongolian government's policies on the development of roads, transport, logistics, and ports in Mongolia, evaluate the current state of development of the roads, transport, and ports sectors, and identify the problems facing these sectors. Based on these analyses, a development concept for the roads and transport sectors of Mongolia is proposed, which aims to connect the central and eastern vertical corridors based on the location of mining and water resources through railways and highway networks, and we identified the need to increase the capacity of ports such as Altanbulag, Sukhbaatar, Khushgiin Khundi, Sainshand, Zamyn-Uud, Ereentsav, Choibalsan, and Bichigt. We also propose the construction of hard and soft infrastructure necessary to connect dry ports of Mongolia with sea ports of China and Russia.

Keywords: China, Russia, Mongolia, transport hub, eastern corridor, railways, highways, roads, air transport, dry ports, seaports, connectivity, soft and hard infrastructure.

1. Policies and activities implemented by the Mongolian government regarding transport, logistics, and port development

In order to establish a dry port on its territory, Mongolia joined the Intergovernmental Agreement on Dry Ports, ratified by the Mongolian State Great Khural on February 5, 2016, and on April 23, 2016, Altanbulag, Ulaanbaatar, Sainshand, and Zamyn-Uud were declared dry ports, and Choibalsan was declared a potential dry port.

Mongolia's long-term development policy "VISION-2050", approved in 2020, sets the following goals: "Implement a multi-center city system, build satellite cities starting with the construction of new cities such as "Aero City" and "Maidar City", fully connect them to the engineering network, intensify housing construction, fully put the new international airport in Ulaanbaatar into operation, and develop it into a North Asian passenger and cargo transportation hub and integrated logistics center." A Northeast Asian integrated freight transportation hub will be established in Aerocity in the Khushgiyin Valley, based on a new international airport, the newly planned Altanbulag-Zamyn-Uud Bogdkhan railway, the AN-3 highway, and major energy network projects. Within this framework, specialized mega warehouses will be built in Argalant-Emeelt, Bagakhangai, and Nalaikh, cargo distribution centers will be established in 9 locations in Ulaanbaatar, and logistics centers will be established in Bayan Urtuu, Argalant-Emeelt, and Aero City.[1, p.23]

Within the framework of implementing these goals, the "New Revitalization Policy" proposes to

implement the following goals of "Develop hard and soft infrastructure of ports to increase cargo and passenger throughput capacity, increase exports, gradually connecting border ports with railways and paved roads, improve the competitiveness of transport and logistics by improving freight traffic, and create the basic conditions for becoming a transit country in the future. Improve the organization of Mongolian airspace and airspace utilization, increase the number of transit aircraft, and gradually continue the liberalization of air transport to create a freight transport hub which will support the tourism sector. Based on Mongolia's regional development concept, increase trade turnover by gradually establishing free economic zones and dry ports.[2, p.7]"

As such, measures are being taken to increase the carrying and throughput capacity of road and transport infrastructure, and to eliminate road and transport congestion and bottlenecks.

Subsequently, the Government approved Resolution No. 327 on measures to be taken regarding the "Five Circles of New Revival" on September 1, 2023. Within the framework of these five circles, the goals are to build roads connecting inter-provincial and border crossings, and to connect border crossing roads connecting Russia and China with paved roads in 5 vertical and 2 horizontal directions, and to expand them in stages.

2. Current condition of Mongolia's road and transport sector

As a landlocked country located between two superpowers, Russia and China, international trade and

transport via land and sea ports are highly dependent on the socio-economic and political environment of the two neighbors and their international political, economic and geopolitical situation. The majority of Mongolia's exports enter the Russian and Chinese markets through Zamyn-Uud, Gashuun Sukhait, Bichigt, and Altanbulag ports, while the majority of Mongolia's domestic imports are through Zamyn-Uud (via railway and motorway), Altanbulag (via motorway) port, and into Ereen Port in China and Khiagt Port in Russia. As the volume of international supply and demand increases, the volume of transit and import and export cargo passing through Zamyn-Uud, Ulaanbaatar, and Altanbulag ports has increased dramatically. However, the transport and logistics capabilities of these ports are insufficient to meet the growing needs of international trade, transit and transport.

From 2013 to 2023, the volume of cargo transported by the Mongolian road transport sector increased by 59.9 million tons (240%), the volume of cargo transported by rail increased by 11.3 million tons (58.8%), and the volume of cargo transported by road increased by 48.6 million tons (330%). Compared to

the volume of cargo transported by air reaching 4 thousand tons in 2013, it increased by 8.6 thousand tons (210%) by 2023. This positive impact is believed to be the result of the new airport in the Khushgyn Valley, which came into operation in 2018 and increased the volume of international cargo transported through it.

Considering the cargo turnover by type of transport: In 2013, railway freight turnover accounted for 49.6%, road freight turnover for 50.3%, and air freight turnover for 0.009% of the total freight turnover in the country, while in 2023, railway freight turnover accounted for 31.6%, road freight turnover for 68.3%, and air freight turnover for 0.008%. While the share of railway freight turnover decreased from 2013 to 2023, the share of road freight turnover increased. This can be considered as a shift in freight turnover from railway to road nationwide.

In other words, the increasing contribution of road to the country's economy can be understood as the result of measures taken by the Mongolian government to increase the capacity of the national and local road network. See Table 1 for indicators of the road and transport sector in Mongolia.

Table 1.

Road and transport sector indicators in Mongolia

Indicator	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Load carried (thousand tons)	42361.4	44636.2	32197.3	40400.2	53983.4	67802.9	68997.5	60297.8	49238.1	60813.4	102302.1
Railway	21035.5	21118.6	19150.8	19989.1	22765.1	25763.3	28143.0	29840.1	31261.4	27680.9	32362.6
Roadway	21321.9	23514.2	13043.7	20406.2	31212.9	42033.8	40848.8	30455.0	17970.3	33075.6	69930.9
Airway	4.1	3.4	2.8	4.9	5.4	5.8	5.8	2.7	6.4	12.9	8.6
Freight turnover (million tons/km)	14641.9	17419.5	13844.3	16619.4	19167.8	21969.5	23601.8	23861.0	20674.6	17534.1	25963.4
Railway	12076.5	12473.7	11462.6	12371.0	13493.3	15315.3	17384.1	19167.6	18345.1	14910.2	18851.0
Roadway	2555.8	4936.4	2374.0	4236.2	5661.3	6640.6	6203.8	4685.3	2313.9	2591.9	7088.1
Airway	9.6	9.4	7.7	12.2	13.2	13.6	13.9	8.1	15.6	32.0	24.3
Number of passengers (million people)	307.9	344.2	260.3	264.4	216.1	197.0	173.0	126.5	107.1	146.3	147.0
Railway	3.8	3.3	2.8	2.7	2.6	2.6	3.0	2.0	0.4	2.4	2.2
Roadway	303.4	340.2	256.5	260.7	212.2	193.0	168.4	124.1	106.5	143.0	143.1
Airway	0.8	0.7	1.0	1.0	1.3	1.4	1.6	0.5	0.2	0.9	1.7
Waterway	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1
Passenger turnover (million person/km)	4604.2	5235.4	4931.6	4988.5	5434.7	6598.1	7146.2	3416.9	1563.4	4445.3	6494.5
Railway	1394.4	1194.5	996.7	955.5	973.2	993.7	1111.5	579.3	90.7	701.5	799.3
Roadway	1897.5	2793.0	1940.5	1959.9	2040.9	2919.9	2925.1	2178.0	1023.0	1914.9	1813.2
Airway	1311.8	1247.1	1993.5	2072.4	2420.2	2684.2	3109.4	659.6	449.4	1828.4	3880.8
Waterway	0.5	0.8	0.9	0.7	0.4	0.3	0.2	0.0	0.4	0.5	1.2

Total transportation revenue (billion tugriks)	1045.0	1038.3	987.9	1191.6	1422.2	1754.4	2384.6	2025.0	2078.1	4435.8	6744.7
Railway	421.4	427.9	387.9	436.9	530.0	616.0	708.6	770.1	766.3	748.2	1124.9
Roadway	376.2	363.8	345.1	467.2	506.4	695.9	1177.2	1090.8	1111.3	3174.0	4676.4
Airway	247.3	246.2	254.3	287.3	385.5	442.3	498.7	164.1	200.1	513.0	941.9

Source: Statistical database of the National Statistics Committee of Mongolia, www,1212,mn

Table 1 shows that from 2013 to 2023 the total passenger traffic transported nationwide decreased by 1.8 million person per km (41.1%), which includes a decrease in railway passenger traffic by 595 thousand person per km (42.7%) and a decrease in road passenger traffic by 84.3 thousand person per km (4.4%), while air passenger traffic increased by 2.5 million person per km (300%) and water passenger traffic increased by 700 person per km (2.4%). These increases in air passenger traffic and water passenger traffic are due to the establishment and operation of the new airport in the Khushgyn Valley and the increase in the number of people traveling on the Sukhbaatar ship in the Khuvsgul Lake. For example, while in 2013, railways accounted for 30.2%, roads for 41.2%, air for 28.5%, and waterways for 0.01% of Mongolia's total passenger transport turnover, in 2023, railways accounted for 12.3%, roads for 27.9%, air for 59.7%, and waterways for 0.01%. This means that the percentage of passenger turnover of railways and roads is decreasing, while the percentage of air passenger turnover is increasing. This is due to the increase in the number of foreign and domestic flights in recent years.

In 2013, the revenue of the Mongolian road and transport sector was 1 billion tugriks, while in 2023 it reached 6.7 billion tugriks, which is an increase of 5.6 billion tugriks, or 6.5 times. In 2013, railway revenue accounted for 40.3%, road revenue for 35.9%, and air revenue for 23.6% of Mongolia's road and transport

sector revenue, while in 2023, railway revenue accounted for 16.7%, road revenue for 69.3%, and air revenue for 13.9%. The decrease in railways share and the increase of almost 2 times in the road revenue share can be attributed to the quality improvement of road infrastructure, especially the opening of the Bayankhongor, Gobi-Altai, and Khovd highways to the western provinces had a tangible impact on the increase in road transport revenue.

Thus, the volume of transported cargo and passenger traffic increased throughout Mongolia. During this period, while the volume of cargo traffic on Mongolian roads, air routes, and waterways increased, the volume of railway freight traffic tended to decrease. We believe that this is due to the deteriorating infrastructure of the railway, outdated machinery and equipment, insufficient capacity of stations, logistics centers and terminals, and the lack of electrification of the railway.

3. Current status of Mongolia's transport brokerage and logistics sector

Mongolia has a total of 39 ports, including 6 railway ports, 4 air ports, and 27 road ports. However, of these only 7 road, 3 rail, and 1 by air ports are operational. According to the World Port Logistics Capacity Index, Mongolia ranks 130th out of 160 countries[3,p.27].

Figure 1.
Current status of Mongolian ports

Currently, there are over 300 registered transport and logistics companies in Mongolia, of which about 120 companies are engaged in permanent operations with about 10000 people working in this sector. 90 percent of Mongolia's total import cargo passes through three ports: Zamyun-Uud, Altanbulag, and Sukhbaatar[3,p.34].

Mongolian imported goods arrive at the Tianjin port of China and are transported through the territory of China, transferred from narrow gauge to wide gauge at the Zamyun-Uud port through Ereen port, and then transported across the territory of Mongolia, delivered to 11 terminals in Ulaanbaatar. After they reach Ulaanbaatar, the goods are unloaded from the wagon at the container yard and passes through customs inspection. Once the recipient pays the tax, the cargo is received, and distributed by car to wholesale and retail centers, and the cargo is delivered to the final consumer. If the recipient cannot pay the tax, the cargo is stored in a bonded warehouse.

After the goods arrive in Ulaanbaatar, there is an urgent need to transport the goods and distribute them to the recipients in a short time. It has become necessary to improve the efficiency of services at Tianjin Port with the cooperation of the Chinese authorities, improve the capacity of the logistics center based on mixed transport, and establish a new logistics center in

an optimal location when organizing services in Zamyun-Uud and Ulaanbaatar.[4,p.57]

Thus, the Mongolian State Congress and the Government are taking necessary measures to develop the transport and logistics and port sectors. One such example is the "Port Revitalization Policy", which prioritizes the development of hard and soft infrastructure of ports, increasing their throughput capacity, laying the foundation for the development of mixed transport, increasing domestic and transit transport flows, and establishing free economic zones. In doing so, the government is focusing on implementing the goals of establishing a free economic zone based on the Khushgyn Valley Airport and establishing an international transport logistics center by building the Bogdhan Railway.

There is a need to propose a new concept of road and transport development based on Mongolia's mineral deposits and groundwater resources. To this end, it is considered necessary to connect the central vertical corridor with the eastern vertical corridor by rail and road way. This can be realized by building a new 540 km railway between Baganuur and Choibalsan, along with the construction of a 394 km railway between Sainshand, Baruun-Urt, and Khoot[4, p.85].

Figure 2.

Mongolia's road and transport development concept

Source: Image created based on the results of dry port research by Davaasuren A.

As can be seen from Figure 2, the development concept of Mongolia's road and transport sector should be based on the location of mining and water resources. Additionally, there is a need to connect the central and eastern vertical corridors by rail (a fully electrified second pair of railways connecting Zamyun-Uud, Khushgyn Valley, and Sukhbaatar along the main line of the Ulaanbaatar railway, including the Bogdhan railway, and a fully electrified railway connecting Bichigt, Khoot, Choibalsan, and Ereentsav) and by road (the vertical axis Asian Highway AN3 highway along the central corridor, the horizontal axis Asian Highway AN32 highway), and to increase the capacity of ports such as Altanbulag, Sukhbaatar, Khushgyn Valley,

Sainshand, Zamyun-Uud, Ereentsav, Choibalsan, and Bichigt by 2-3 times [5, p. 19].

Conclusion

While the volume of road, air and passenger traffic transported throughout Mongolia is increasing, the volume of rail freight traffic has decreased. This is due to the deterioration of the railway infrastructure, outdated equipment and machinery, insufficient capacity of stations, intermodal logistics centers and terminals, and the lack of electrification of the railways.

The capacity of ports along the Central Corridor of Mongolia has become overused and can no longer cope with the load. Additionally, projects to increase the throughput capacity of Mongolian ports

implemented by the World Bank, ADB and other international organizations are not aimed at improving the technical, administrative, organizational management, ownership and human resource capacity of UN-locked dry ports, and are therefore ineffective.

Hence, there is an urgent need to review Mongolia's road, transport, logistics, and port development vision, connect our country's ports based on mineral and water resources with mixed transport infrastructure, improve the throughput capacity of ports, and connect them with seaports in Russia and China.

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